

EFFECT OF REDUCED RATES OF RECOMMENDED FERTILIZER ON THE CULTIVATION OF BINA DHAN 7

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted at the Soil Science Field Laboratory of Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during *Aman* season of 2011 to investigate the effect of reduced rates of recommended fertilizer on BINA dhan7. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. There were 7 treatments such as T₁ : Control, T₂ : Recommended Fertilizer Dose (RFD), T₃ : 40% RFD, T₄ : 60% RFD, T₅ : 80% RFD, T₆ : 120% RFD and T₇ : 140% RFD. In this experiment 80 kg N, 25 kg P, 32 kg K, 9 kg S and 3 kg Zn ha⁻¹ were applied in the form of urea, TSP, MOP, gypsum and zinc sulfate, respectively as per the Recommended Fertilizer Dose (RFD). The Grain and straw yields of BINA dhan7 were significantly affected due to different treatments. The highest grain yield (5.52 t ha⁻¹) and straw yield (4.99 t ha⁻¹) were observed in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD) which was statistically identical to that in treatment T₆ (120% RFD) in both cases. The content of N, P, K and S of BINA dhan7 were significantly influenced due to different treatments under study. Nutrient uptake by grain and straw on BINA dhan7 was significantly influenced by different treatments in the experiment. It was observed that application of reduced rates of recommended fertilizer decreased nutrient content and nutrient uptake by grain and straw compared to that in treatment T₂ (RFD). Though the highest yield was obtained in T₇ (140% RFD) treatment but the yield was statistically identical to T₂ (RFD) treatment.

Key words: BINA dhan 7, nutrient content, nutrient uptake, yield

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most important cereals in the world. It is the staple food for more than half of the world population and grown in more than 100 countries. China, India, Indonesia, Bangladesh, Thailand and Vietnam produce about 80% of the world rice production. Among the leading rice growing countries of the world, Bangladesh ranks fourth in both rice area and production (BRRI, 2007). In Bangladesh, rice accounts for 95% of the annual food grain production. Rice is not only the staple food but also provides nearly 40% of total national employment (48% of total rural employment), about 75% of the calories and 55% of the protein in the average daily diet of the people of the country.

The yield of rice is very low in Bangladesh (3.34 t ha⁻¹) compared to 9.65, 6.59, 6.70 and 6.92 t ha⁻¹ in Australia, Korean Republic, Japan and Spain, respectively (FAO, 2002). Rice production is decreasing day by day due to high population pressure. To maintain self-sufficiency in rice, Bangladesh needs to expand rice production by raising yields at a rate that is at least equal to population growth until the demand for rice has stabilized. Therefore, attempts should be taken to increase the yield per unit area by applying improved technology and proper management of fertilizers to achieve the goal.

Nutrients supplying of soils are gradually declining over time due to intensive cropping with high yielding rice varieties. Practically no soil can sustain high crop yields for an indefinite period from its own nutrient reserves. Even the most fertile soils can do so only for certain years and at one time the yield will be declined due to deficiency of some nutrients. N, P and K are the primary macronutrients and play a key role to increase the production of rice. Among the plant nutrients, N deserves special attention because of its large requirement by crop and instability in soil. N influences the growth, yield and yield components of rice. This important element has been found to be at deficient levels in most agricultural soils of Bangladesh. P is the second major nutrient for plant and plays a critical role in the life cycle of plants. Adequate P nutrition

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enhances the fundamental process of photosynthesis, N-fixation, flowering, fruiting and maturation. But P is widely deficient in Bangladesh soils. K is the third major food elements for plant. It is necessary for the synthesis of protein and starch, normal cell division and growth. Its deficiency may greatly reduce crop yield. S plays a unique role in plant metabolism.

In this experiment, reduced rates of recommended fertilizer are used to find out their effects on yield and yield contributing characters of BINA dhan 7. If reduction of combined fertilizer application gives statistically identical yield compared to recommended fertilizer dose, their reduced rates may be used easily, not only to maintain soil health and sustainable agriculture but also it becomes ecologically sound, environmentally friendly and economically feasible. Considering the above points, the present study was, therefore, undertaken to study the effect of reduced rates of recommended fertilizer on the growth, yield and yield contributing characters of rice - BINA dhan7 and nutrient content and uptake by rice-BINA dhan7.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site and test crop

The experiment was set up at the Soil Science Field Laboratory of Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during the *Aman* season of 2011. The test crop in this experiment was rice - BINA dhan7.

Soil sampling and analysis

Initial and post-harvest soil samples were collected at a depth of 0-15 cm from the Soil Science Field Laboratory of Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. After proper sampling soil was taken for physical and chemical analysis. Physical analysis of soil was done by hydrometer method and the textural class was determined by fitting to the Marshall's triangular co-ordinate following USDA system. Soil pH was measured as described as by Jackson (1962). Organic carbon was determined by the method of Walkley and Black (1934) and the organic matter content was calculated by multiplying the percent organic carbon with the Van Bemmelen factor of 1.73. Cation exchange capacity was determined as outlined by Jackson (1962). Total N content of soil was estimated following the micro-Kjeldahl method (Page *et al.*, 1982). Available P was measured following Olsen *et al.* (1954). Exchangeable K, Na and Ca were determined by following the method as described by Black (1965). Available S was determined turbidimetrically described by Page *et al.* (1982).

Experimental protocol

There were 7 treatments such as T₁ : Control, T₂ : Recommended Fertilizer Dose (RFD), T₃ : 40% RFD, T₄ : 60% RFD, T₅ : 80% RFD, T₆ : 120% RFD and T₇ : 140% RFD. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four replications. Thus the total number of unit plots was 28. The size of each unit plot was 4m x 2.5m. After final land preparation the experimental plot was fertilized to each plot as per experimental treatment. The recommended doses for N, P, K, S and Zn were applied in the form of urea, TSP, MOP, gypsum and zinc sulfate according to recommendation of BINA (2010). Thirty five days old healthy seedlings were transplanted in the plots on 12 August 2011. The spacing of transplanting was 20 cm x 20 cm and three seedlings were transplanted in each hill. Intercultural operations were done for ensuring and maintaining the normal growth of the crop as per recommendation of BINA (2010). The crop was harvested at full maturity on 8 December 2011 and data were recorded following appropriate procedure.

Chemical analysis of rice grain and straw

The Grain and straw samples were analyzed for determination of N, P, K and S content and were determined following the same methods used in soil chemical analysis.

Statistical analysis

The analysis of variance for various crop characters and also for various nutrients content and nutrient uptake was done following the F-test. Mean comparisons of the treatments were made by the Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of different treatments on yield components and yield of rice - BINA dhan7

Plant height

The plant height of BINA dhan7 was significantly affected due to different treatments (Table 1). Plant height varied from 72.78 cm in T₁ (control) treatment to 88.20 cm in T₇ (140% RFD) treatment. The tallest plant (88.20 cm) was recorded in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD) which was statistically similar to the treatments T₂ (RFD) and T₆ (120% RFD) with the values of 85.85 and 86.98 cm, respectively. This finding might be due to smaller reduction of all the fertilizers, which did not affect the growth and development of plants remarkably. The shortest plant (72.78 cm) was obtained in the treatment T₁ (control) which was followed by the treatments T₃ (40% RFD) and T₄ (60% RFD). Greater reduction (60%) of N, P, K, S and Zn fertilizers from recommended rates greatly reduced plant growth and development which resulted in shorter plant. The results are also in agreement with the findings of Moreno *et al.* (1985).

Table 1. Effect of reduced rates of recommended fertilizers on the yield contributing characters of rice - BINA dhan7

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Effective tiller hill ⁻¹	Filled grain panicle ⁻¹	Unfilled grain panicle ⁻¹	Weight of 1000 grain (g)
T ₁ :Control	72.78d	21.38d	7.70d	66.18d	14.45a	22.31a
T ₂ : RFD	85.85ab	25.18ab	12.08ab	101.25ab	12.90a	23.00a
T ₃ :40% RFD	80.50c	23.20c	9.33c	82.40c	13.90a	22.59a
T ₄ :60% RFD	81.18c	23.80bc	10.88b	88.85c	13.00a	22.70a
T ₅ :80% RFD	84.43b	24.78abc	11.70ab	92.45bc	13.16a	22.91a
T ₆ :120% RFD	86.98ab	25.73a	12.25ab	107.13a	12.93a	23.10a
T ₇ :140% RFD	88.20a	25.90a	12.75a	106.70a	13.40a	22.95aa
SE±	0.99	0.35	0.36	2.86	0.21	0.10

Figure (s) in a column having common letters do not differ significantly at 5% level of significance and the figures which are not lettered are non-significant at 5% level of significance. Recommended Fertilizer Dose (RFD) = 80 kg N ha⁻¹+ 25 kg P ha⁻¹+ 32 kg K ha⁻¹+ 9 kg S ha⁻¹+ 3 kg Zn ha⁻¹

Panicle length

Panicle length of BINA dhan7 was significantly influenced by different treatments (Table 1). Panicle length due to different treatments varied from 21.38 cm in T₁ (control) to 25.90 cm in T₇ (140%RFD). The values for panicle length of all the treatments were higher than that of the control. The panicles of T₂ (RFD) to T₇ (140% RFD) treatments were about 1.82 to 4.52 cm taller than that found in treatment T₁ (control).

Effective tillers hill⁻¹

There was a significant effect of different fertilizer treatments on the effective tillers hill⁻¹ of rice plants (Table 1). The number of tillers hill⁻¹ due to different treatments varied from 7.70 to 12.75. The highest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (12.75) was found in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD) which was statistically similar to the treatments T₂ (RFD), T₅ (80% RFD) and T₆ (120% RFD) with values of 12.08, 11.70 and 12.25, respectively. The minimum number of tillers hill⁻¹ (7.70) was found in the treatment T₁ (control). Due to reduced rate of N, P, K, S and Zn, the number of tillers hill⁻¹ (9.33) was reduced in the treatment of T₃ (40% RFD) followed by T₄ (60% RFD) treatment. This might be due to smaller reduction of the chemical fertilizers from recommended rates, which affected the growth and development of plants.

Filled grains panicle⁻¹

Data presented in Table 1 showed a significant effect of different treatments on the number of filled grains panicle⁻¹ of BINA dhan7. The number of filled grains panicle⁻¹ of different treatments ranged from 66.18 to 107.13. The highest number of filled grains panicle⁻¹ (107.13) was obtained from T₆ (120% RFD) treatment, which was statistically similar to those recorded in the treatments T₂ (RFD) and T₇ (140% RFD) with values of 101.25 and 106.70, respectively. The lowest number of filled grains panicle⁻¹ (66.18) was obtained from the treatment T₁ (control), which was followed by the treatment T₃ (40% RFD) and T₄ (60% RFD). The panicle length was reduced with the decreasing rates of fertilizers from the RFD values.

Unfilled grains panicle⁻¹

The variation in the number of unfilled grains panicle⁻¹ due to different treatments was non-significant (Table 1). The results indicated that the number of unfilled grains panicle⁻¹ varied from 12.90 to 14.45. The highest number of unfilled grains panicle⁻¹ (14.45) was produced by the treatment T₁ (control). It indicates that no application of N, P, K, S and Zn fertilizers produced the highest number of unfilled grains. The lowest number of unfilled grains panicle⁻¹ (12.90) was produced by the treatment T₂ (RFD).

Weight of 1000-grain

There was non-significant effect of different treatments on the 1000-grain weight of BINA dhan7. The 1000-grain weight ranged from 22.31 to 23.10 g. The highest 1000-grain weight (23.10 g) was recorded from T₆ (120% RFD), while the lowest 1000-grain weight (22.31g) was obtained in the treatment T₁ (control).

Grain yield

Grain yield of BINA dhan7 responded significantly to different treatments (Table 2). The grain yield ranged from 3.19 to 5.52 t ha⁻¹. All the treatments showed higher value over control. The highest grain yield (5.52 t ha⁻¹) was obtained in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD) which was statistically similar to the treatments T₂ (RFD) and T₆ (120% RFD) with values of 5.51 and 5.29 t ha⁻¹, respectively. The lowest grain yield (3.19 t ha⁻¹) was obtained from T₁ (control) which was statistically different from all other treatments. It was noted that, these nutrients had significant role on grain yield. The percentages of increased grain yield over control due to different treatments were also presented in the Table 2. The highest percentage (73.04%) of increased grain yield over control was recorded in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD). The lowest percentage (13.79%) of increased grain yield over control was recorded in the treatment T₃ (40% RFD). The grain yield obtained from different treatments ranked in the order of T₇ > T₂ > T₆ > T₅ > T₄ > T₃ > T₁.

Table 2: Effect of reduced rates of recommended fertilizer on the yield of BINA dhan7

Treatments	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	% increase over control	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	% increase over control
T ₁ : Control	3.19e		2.87f	
T ₂ : RFD	5.51a	72.73	4.69bc	63.41
T ₃ :40% RFD	3.63d	13.79	3.28e	14.29
T ₄ :60% RFD	4.94c	54.86	4.23d	47.39
T ₅ :80% RFD	5.14bc	61.13	4.52cd	57.49
T ₆ :120% RFD	5.29ab	65.83	4.90ab	70.73
T ₇ :140% RFD	5.52a	73.04	4.99a	73.87
SE±	0.17		0.15	

Figure (s) in a column having common letter (s) do not differ significantly at 5% level of significance. Recommended Fertilizer Dose (RFD) = 80 kg N ha⁻¹ + 25 kg P ha⁻¹ + 32 kg K ha⁻¹ + 9 kg S ha⁻¹ + 3 kg Zn ha⁻¹

Straw yield

Results presented in Table 2 showed that straw yield of BINA dhan7 was significantly influenced by different treatments under study. The straw yield obtained from different treatments ranged from 2.87 to 4.99 t ha⁻¹. All the treatments gave the higher straw yield over control. It was observed that the treatments T₇ (140% RFD) gave the highest straw yield (4.99 t ha⁻¹) which was statistically similar to that in the treatment T₆ (120% RFD) with values of 4.90 t ha⁻¹. The lowest straw yield (2.87 t ha⁻¹) was recorded in the treatment T₁ (Control). The highest percentage (73.87%) of increased straw yield over control was noted in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD). The percentages of increased straw yield over control due to various treatments used in the experiment were also presented in the Table 2. The straw yield due to different treatments ranked in the order of T₇ > T₆ > T₂ > T₅ > T₄ > T₃ > T₁.

Nutrient content in rice grain and straw

Nitrogen

There was significant influence of different treatments on N concentration of both rice grain and straw (Table 3). The content of N in grain varied from 1.09 to 1.18%. The treatment T₆ (120% RFD) resulted the maximum N content in grain (1.18%). The minimum value (1.09%) was recorded in the treatment T₁ (control). The content of N in straw ranged from 0.64 to 0.87% (Table 3). The highest value (0.87%) was found in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD). The lowest value (0.64%) was noted in the treatment T₁ (control), T₃ (40% RFD) and T₄ (60% RFD). The RFD increased N content in both grain and straw of rice but smaller (40%) to greater (80%) reduction of N, P, K, S and Zn fertilizers affected N content of grain and straw significantly. It indicates that the recommended fertilizer dose had pronounced effect on N content in both grain and straw but the reduction of the fertilizers from the recommended fertilizer dose affected significantly in N content.

Table 3. N, P, K and S contents in grain and straw of BINA dhan7 as influenced by reduced rates of recommended fertilizer

Treatment	N (%)		P (%)		K (%)		S (%)	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
T ₁ : control	1.09a	0.64d	0.18c	0.044d	0.17b	1.58d	0.17bc	0.15c
T ₂ : RFD	1.13a	0.81ab	0.22a	0.068ab	0.21a	1.88a	0.20a	0.21a
T ₃ : 40% RFD	1.12a	0.64d	0.17c	0.053cd	0.17b	1.85a	0.15c	0.15c
T ₄ :60% RFD	1.12a	0.64d	0.12b	0.053cd	0.17b	1.73c	0.20a	0.16b
T ₅ :80% RFD	1.18a	0.70cd	0.20b	0.061bc	0.20a	1.83ab	0.19a	0.20ab
T ₆ :120% RFD	1.18a	0.76bc	0.12b	0.065ab	0.17b	1.78bc	0.19a	0.21a
T ₇ :140% RFD	1.13a	0.87a	0.21ab	0.072a	0.21a	1.83ab	0.16b	0.21a

Figure (s) in a column having common letter (s) do not differ significantly at 5% level of Significance. Recommended Fertilizer Dose (RFD) = 80 kg N ha⁻¹ + 25 kg P ha⁻¹ + 32 kg K ha⁻¹ + 9 kg S ha⁻¹ + 3 kg Zn ha⁻¹.

Phosphorus

The content of P in grain ranged from 0.17 to 0.22%. The highest P value (0.22%) was recorded in the treatment T₂ (RFD) and the lowest value (0.172%) was noted in the treatment T₃ (40% RFD). All the treatments showed increased P content in grain over treatment T₃ (40% RFD). The P content in straw varied from 0.044% to 0.072% (Table 3). All the treatments showed increased P content in straw over control. The highest P value (0.072%) was found in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD). The lowest P value (0.044%) was observed in the treatment T₁ (control). The content of P in grain was higher than that of straw in all the treatments. It indicates that the recommended fertilizer dose had pronounced effect on P content in both grain and straw and the reduction of the fertilizers from the recommended fertilizer dose affected significantly in P content. Similar results were also obtained by Kadu *et al.* (1991).

Potassium

Potassium (K) content in both grain and straw was significantly affected by different treatments (Table 3). Potassium content in grain varied from 0.17 to 0.21%. The highest K content (0.21%) was found in the treatment T₂ (RFD) and T₇ (140% RFD). The lowest K content (0.17%) was recorded in the treatment T₁ (control), T₃ (40% RFD), T₄ (60% RFD) and T₆ (120% RFD). The K content in straw varied from 1.58 to 1.88% (Table 3). The highest K content (1.88%) was found in the treatment T₂ (RFD). The lowest K content (1.58%) was observed in the treatment T₁ (control). It is observed that K content in straw was higher than that of grains in all the treatments. It indicates that the recommended fertilizer dose had significant effect on K content in both grain and straw and the reduction of the fertilizers from the recommended fertilizer dose affected significantly in K content. The application of recommended fertilizer dose performed better in increasing K content both in grain and straw of BINA dhan7. The results were also in agreement with the findings of Sachdev *et al.* (1983).

Sulphur

Results in Table 3 indicated that sulphur (S) content in both grain and the straw of BINA dhan7 was significantly influenced by different treatments used in the experiment. S content in grain ranged from 0.15 to 0.20%. The highest S content (0.20%) in grain was found in the treatment T₂ (RFD) and T₄ (60% RFD). The lowest S content (0.15%) was recorded in the treatment T₃ (40% RFD). In straw, sulphur content varied from 0.15 to 0.21%. The highest S content (0.21%) was recorded in the treatment T₂ (RFD), T₆ (120% RFD) and T₇ (140% RFD). The lowest S content (0.15%) was noted in the treatment T₁ (control) and T₃ (40% RFD). It indicates that the recommended fertilizer dose had pronounced effect on S content in both grain and straw and the reduction of the fertilizers from the recommended fertilizer dose affected significantly in S content.

Nutrient uptake by rice

Nitrogen

The uptake of N by grain varied from 34.78 to 62.49 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4). The highest N uptake (62.49 kg ha⁻¹) by grain was recorded in the treatment T₆ (120% RFD) which was statistically identical to that recorded in the treatments T₂ (RFD), T₅ (80% RFD) and T₇ (140% RFD) with N uptake of 62.16, 60.42 and 62.30 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. The lowest N uptake (34.78 kg ha⁻¹) by grain was obtained in the treatment T₁ (control) which was statistically different from all other treatments. In straw, the uptake of N ranged from 18.42 to 43.31 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4). The highest N uptake (43.31 kg ha⁻¹) by straw was observed in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD) which was significantly different from all other treatments. The lowest N uptake (18.42 kg ha⁻¹) by straw was recorded in the treatment T₁ (control) which was statistically different from all other treatments except T₃ (40% RFD).

Phosphorus

The ranges of P uptake in grain were from 5.56 to 12.03 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4). The maximum P uptake (12.03 kg ha⁻¹) by grain was recorded in the treatment T₂ (RFD) which was significantly different from all other treatments except T₇ (140% RFD). The minimum P uptake (5.56 kg ha⁻¹) by grain was observed in the treatment T₁ (control). In straw, the uptake of P varied from 1.26 to 3.61 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4). The highest P uptake (3.61 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD) which was statistically identical to that recorded in the treatments T₂ (RFD) and T₆ (120% RFD). The lowest P uptake (1.26 kg ha⁻¹) was found in the treatment T₁ (control).

Table 4: Effect of reduced rates of recommended fertilizer on the N, P, K and S uptake by BINA dhan7

Treatment	N Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		P Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		K Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		S Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
T ₁ : control	34.78d	18.42e	5.56c	1.26e	5.47e	45.24e	5.37c	4.27d
T ₂ : RFD	62.16a	38.05b	12.03a	3.16ab	11.37a	87.84ab	10.93a	9.70a
T ₃ : 40% RFD	40.48c	21.17e	6.22c	1.72de	6.11d	60.64d	5.46c	4.84d
T ₄ : 60% RFD	55.30b	27.24d	9.73b	2.22cd	8.38c	73.01c	9.89b	6.88c
T ₅ : 80% RFD	60.42a	31.58c	10.35b	2.73bc	10.07b	82.44b	9.64b	8.90b
T ₆ : 120% RFD	62.49a	37.04b	10.40b	3.19ab	8.97c	87.00ab	9.89b	10.39a
T ₇ : 140% RFD	62.30a	43.31a	11.36a	3.61a	11.43a	91.14a	9.08b	10.37a
SE±	2.12	1.67	0.45	0.16	0.44	3.10	0.41	0.47

Figure (s) in a column having common letter (s) do not differ significantly at 5% level of Significance. Recommended Fertilizer Dose (RFD) = 80 kg N ha⁻¹ + 25 kg P ha⁻¹ + 32 kg K ha⁻¹ + 9 kg S ha⁻¹ + 3 kg Zn ha⁻¹.

Potassium

Potassium uptake by BINA dhan7 in both grain and straw was significantly influenced by various treatments (Table 4). The uptake of K by grain varied from 5.47 to 11.43 kg ha⁻¹. The highest K uptake (11.43 kg ha⁻¹) by grain was noted in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD) which was statistically identical to that recorded in the treatment T₂ (RFD) with K uptake of 11.37 kg ha⁻¹. The lowest K uptake (5.47 kg ha⁻¹) by grain was obtained in

the treatment T₁ (control) which was statistically different from all other treatments. In straw, uptake of K ranged from 45.24 to 91.14 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4). The highest K (91.14 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in the treatment T₇ (140% RFD) which was statistically identical to that recorded in the treatment T₂ (RFD) and T₆ (120% RFD) with K uptake of 87.84 and 87.00 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. The lowest K uptake (45.24 kg ha⁻¹) by straw was obtained in the treatment T₁ (control). It was observed that K uptake by rice straw was much higher than that of K uptake by rice grain.

Sulphur

Sulphur uptake by BINA dhan7 in both grain and straw was significantly influenced by various treatments (Table 4). The uptake of S by grain varied from 5.37 to 10.93 kg ha⁻¹. The highest uptake of S (10.93 kg ha⁻¹) by grain was noted in the treatment T₂ (RFD) which was statistically different from all other treatments. The lowest S uptake (5.37 kg ha⁻¹) by grain was obtained in the treatment T₁ (control) which was statistically identical to that recorded in the treatment T₃ (40% RFD). In straw, uptake of S ranged from 4.27 to 10.39 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4.4). The highest S uptake (10.39 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in the treatment T₆ (120% RFD) which was statistically identical to that recorded in the treatment T₂ (RFD) and T₇ (140% RFD) with S uptake of 9.70 and 10.37 kg ha⁻¹ respectively. The lowest S uptake (4.27 kg ha⁻¹) by straw was obtained in the treatment T₁ (control).

The experimental findings revealed that, BINA dhan7 could be cultivated successfully by applying 140% RFD at BAU soil but the yield of this variety is statistically identical to that recorded in the T₂ (RFD) treatment.

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